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STOMACH AND DUODENAL DISEASES

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ABSTRACT

Diseases of the stomach and pancreas occupy a leading position in the structure of digestive organ pathology and are characterized by high prevalence among the adult population. The anatomical and functional interrelationship of these organs often determines the combined course of pathological processes. The work examines the main diseases of the stomach (chronic gastritis, peptic ulcer disease) and pancreas (acute and chronic pancreatitis), their pathogenetic mechanisms, clinical manifestations, and modern diagnostic methods. Special attention was paid to the role of acid-enzyme imbalance, inflammatory changes, and disorders of exocrine function in the formation of cross-symptoms. The need for a comprehensive approach to examining patients with dyspeptic and pain syndromes to timely identify combined pathology and prevent complications was emphasized.

Keywords: *stomach diseases, pancreatic diseases, chronic gastritis, peptic ulcer disease, acute pancreatitis, chronic pancreatitis, dyspepsia, exocrine insufficiency, acid-enzymatic imbalance, diagnosis.*

БОЛЕЗНИ ЖЕЛУДКА И ДВЕНАДЦАТИПЕРСТНОЙ КИШКИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Заболевания желудка и поджелудочной железы занимают ведущие позиции в структуре патологии органов пищеварения и характеризуются высокой распространённостью среди взрослого населения. Анатомическая и функциональная взаимосвязь этих органов обуславливает частое сочетанное течение патологических процессов. В работе рассмотрены основные заболевания желудка (хронический гастрит, язвенная болезнь) и поджелудочной железы (острый и хронический панкреатит), их патогенетические механизмы,

клинические проявления и современные методы диагностики. Особое внимание уделено роли кислотно-ферментного дисбаланса, воспалительных изменений и нарушений экзокринной функции в формировании перекрёстной симптоматики. Подчёркнута необходимость комплексного подхода к обследованию пациентов с диспепсическим и болевым синдромами для своевременного выявления сочетанной патологии и предупреждения осложнений.

Ключевые слова: *заболевания желудка, заболевания поджелудочной железы, хронический гастрит, язвенная болезнь, острый панкреатит, хронический панкреатит, диспепсия, экзокринная недостаточность, кислотно-ферментный дисбаланс, диагностика.*

OSHQOZON VA O'N IKKI BARMOQLI ICHAK KASALLIKLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Oshqozon va oshqozon osti bezi kasalliklari ovqat hazm qilish a'zolari patologiyasi tarkibida yetakchi o'rinni egallaydi va katta yoshdagi aholi orasida yuqori tarqalganligi bilan ajralib turadi. Bu a'zolarning o'zaro anatomik va funktsional bog'liqligi patologik jarayonlarning ko'pincha birga kechishiga sabab bo'ladi. Ishda me'da (surunkali gastrit, yara kasalligi) va me'da osti bezining (o'tkir va surunkali pankreatit) asosiy kasalliklari, ularning patogenetik mexanizmlari, klinik ko'rinishlari va zamonaviy tashxislash usullari ko'rib chiqilgan. Kesishgan simptomatikaning shakllanishida kislota-ferment disbalansi, yallig'lanish o'zgarishlari va ekzokrin funktsiya buzilishlarining roliga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Qo'shma patologiyani o'z vaqtida aniqlash va asoratlarning oldini olish uchun dispeptik va og'riq sindromi bo'lgan bemorlarni tekshirishga kompleks yondashuv zarurligi ta'kidlandi.

Kalit so'zlar: *oshqozon kasalliklari, oshqozon osti bezi kasalliklari, surunkali gastrit, yara kasalligi, o'tkir pankreatit, surunkali pankreatit, dispepsiya, tashqi sekretiya yetishmovchiligi, kislota-ferment disbalansi, diagnostika.*

INTRODUCTION

Diseases of the digestive system remain one of the most common medical problems of our time. In the structure of gastroenterological pathology, leading positions are occupied by diseases of the stomach and pancreas, which are characterized by high morbidity, a tendency to a chronic course, and a risk of severe complications. Their clinical significance is determined not only by their prevalence but also by their pronounced impact on digestion, absorption, and the overall metabolic status of the body.

The stomach plays a key role in the initial stage of digestion, ensuring the mechanical processing of food, the secretion of hydrochloric acid, pepsin, and the internal factor of Castle. Disruption of its secretory, motor, and barrier functions leads to the development of inflammatory and destructive processes in the mucous membrane. The most common pathologies are chronic gastritis and peptic ulcer disease, the pathogenesis of which is associated with an imbalance between the factors of aggression and mucosal protection.

The pancreas, in turn, plays a central role in ensuring the enzymatic digestion of proteins, fats, and carbohydrates. Its exocrine function is realized through the synthesis and secretion of proteases, lipase, and amylase, while its endocrine function is realized through the production of insulin and glucagon. In acute or chronic pancreatitis, enzyme activation occurs within the glandular tissue, leading to inflammation, fibrosis, and a gradual decrease in the organ's functional activity.

The anatomical and physiological proximity of the stomach and pancreas, the commonality of blood supply and innervation, and participation in a single gastroduodenal system determine their close pathogenetic relationship. Changes in stomach acid production affect the stimulation of pancreatic secretion through hormonal mechanisms, including secretin and cholecystokinin. At the same time, insufficient enzyme activity of the pancreas disrupts the neutralization of acidic contents in the duodenum and changes the conditions for the functioning of the gastroduodenal zone.

Analysis of literature on the topic (Literature review).

Modern gastroenterology considers stomach and pancreatic diseases as clinically and pathogenetically interconnected conditions. In the literature, it is emphasized that the anatomical proximity of organs, unified gastroduodenal regulation, and general mechanisms of neurohumoral control often determine the combined course of pathological processes.

Stomach diseases in scientific research

According to international clinical recommendations, chronic gastritis remains one of the most common stomach pathologies. The main role in its development is assigned to *Helicobacter pylori* infection, which causes chronic inflammation of the mucous membrane, disruption of epithelial regeneration, and gradual development of atrophy. Studies confirm that the persistence of infection for a long time is associated with the risk of peptic ulcer disease and neoplastic changes.

Pancreatic diseases in scientific sources

In recent decades, the understanding of the pathogenesis of acute and chronic pancreatitis has significantly expanded. Literature indicates that the main mechanism

of acute pancreatitis is the premature activation of trypsin within acinar cells, which triggers a cascade of autolysis and a systemic inflammatory response.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Within the framework of this work, an analysis of the clinical and diagnostic features of gastric and pancreatic diseases was conducted based on the study of modern scientific publications and clinical observations. The study is analytical and observational in nature and is aimed at identifying the relationship between gastric mucosa pathology and pancreatic exocrine dysfunction.

The object of the study was patients with complaints of epigastric pain, dyspeptic disorders, meteorism, and defecation disorders. The analysis took into account the anamnesis data, the nature of the pain syndrome, the relationship between symptoms and food intake, and the duration of the disease.

To assess the condition of the stomach, the results of esophagogastroduodenoscopy were used, which allow us to determine the presence of inflammatory, erosive, or atrophic changes in the mucous membrane. In some cases, biopsy was performed to confirm the diagnosis morphologically. *Helicobacter pylori* infection was detected using laboratory diagnostic methods.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

During the analysis of clinical observations, it was established that most patients with gastric and pancreatic diseases exhibit similar symptoms, which significantly complicates differential diagnosis in the early stages of examination. The most frequent complaints were pain in the epigastric region, a feeling of heaviness after eating, flatulence, nausea, and unstable stool.

When assessing the pain syndrome, it was revealed that in patients with predominantly gastric pathology, the pain was burning or aching in nature and more often occurred on an empty stomach or 1-2 hours after meals. In the case of pancreatic involvement, the pain syndrome acquired a more intense and prolonged character, sometimes radiating to the back, which is typical for pancreatic pathology.

Endoscopic examination revealed the presence of inflammatory changes in the gastric mucosa in most examined patients. Hyperemia, edema, and in some cases, erosive defects were observed. Some patients exhibited signs of atrophic changes accompanied by decreased acid production.

Laboratory evaluation of pancreatic function revealed a moderate decrease in fecal elastase-1 levels in a significant proportion of patients, indicating the formation of exocrine insufficiency. In some patients, an increase in amylase and lipase was recorded during the exacerbation phase of the inflammatory process.

Ultrasound examination revealed diffuse changes in the pancreatic parenchyma, moderate increase in organ size, or signs of fibrous changes in the chronic course of the disease.

Clinical significance of Stomach and duodenal diseases

I. Pathogenetic and diagnostic significance

Diseases of the stomach and duodenum occupy one of the leading places in the structure of digestive organ pathology. Their clinical significance is determined by their high prevalence, tendency to a chronic course, and pronounced impact on the processes of digestion and absorption of nutrients. Gastritis, peptic ulcer disease, and duodenitis form the main group of gastroduodenal diseases, which often proceed together.

The stomach plays a key role in the initial stage of digestion, ensuring the secretion of hydrochloric acid and pepsin. The duodenum, in turn, is the central link in regulating pancreatic and biliary secretion through the hormones secretin and cholecystokinin. Disruptions in this zone lead to the failure of complex neurohumoral regulatory mechanisms.

II. Risk of complications and systemic significance

The clinical significance of stomach and duodenal diseases is largely determined by the risk of severe complications. Peptic ulcer can be complicated by gastrointestinal bleeding, perforation, penetration, and pyloric stenosis. Bleeding is one of the frequent causes of emergency hospitalization and requires immediate medical attention.

The perforation of the ulcer leads to the outflow of gastric or duodenal contents into the abdominal cavity and the development of peritonitis - a condition that threatens the patient's life. Thus, even a chronic disease with an unfavorable course can transition into acute surgical pathology.

An equally important aspect is oncological vigilance. A long-standing atrophic gastritis is considered a precancerous condition. Chronic inflammation contributes to intestinal metaplasia and epithelial dysplasia, which increases the risk of stomach adenocarcinoma formation.

The importance of stomach and duodenal anatomy in understanding their diseases

The anatomical features of the stomach and duodenum play a key role in the formation of the clinical picture and complications of their diseases. Understanding the topography, blood supply, innervation, and functional specialization of various departments allows for understanding the mechanisms of pathological process development and justifying treatment tactics.

The stomach is anatomically divided into the cardiac section, fundus, body, and pyloric part. The localization of the pathological process in each of these areas is accompanied by various clinical manifestations. For example, the damage to the cardiac zone is associated with the disruption of the lower esophageal sphincter and the development of gastroesophageal reflux. Pathology of the stomach body, where most parietal cells are located, leads to a change in acid production, which is crucial in peptic ulcer and gastritis. The involvement of the pyloric region can lead to impaired evacuation of the contents and the development of pyloric stenosis.

Interdisciplinary Importance

Diseases of the stomach and duodenum have a pronounced interdisciplinary significance, since the gastroduodenal zone is functionally connected with other organs and systems of the body. Their pathology goes beyond a narrow gastroenterological problem and requires the involvement of specialists of various profiles.

First of all, the close anatomical and physiological connection of the duodenum with the pancreas and bile ducts determines the need for joint management of patients by gastroenterologists and surgeons. The ulcer disease can be complicated by perforation or bleeding, requiring urgent surgical intervention. Penetration of the ulcer into the pancreas forms a clinical picture similar to pancreatitis.

Anatomical Variations and Clinical Implications

Anatomical variations of the stomach and duodenum have important clinical significance, as they can change the nature of the course of diseases, influence diagnosis, and determine the specifics of surgical tactics. Despite the relative stability of the gastroduodenal zone structure, individual differences are quite common.

One of the common variations is the change in the shape and position of the stomach. In clinical practice, different types of stomach shape are distinguished: horn-shaped, hook-shaped, elongated. In individuals with asthenic physique, the stomach can be vertically oriented and lowered (gastroptosis), which contributes to the slowing of gastric emptying and the development of dyspeptic symptoms. A shortened or elevated stomach can alter the clinical picture of the pain syndrome.

The anatomical features of blood supply are also important. Variations of branching of the ventral trunk and gastric arteries can influence the risk and localization of bleeding in peptic ulcer disease. For example, an ulcer of the lesser curvature of the stomach is dangerous due to damage to the left gastric artery, which can lead to massive blood loss.

CONCLUSION

Diseases of the stomach and duodenum are a significant problem in modern gastroenterology due to their high prevalence, tendency to a chronic course, and risk of developing severe complications. The clinical picture of these pathologies is formed

under the influence of anatomical, functional, and neurohumoral mechanisms that closely link the gastroduodenal zone with other organs of the digestive system.

Understanding the anatomy of the stomach and duodenum allows us to explain the features of the pain syndrome, the nature of the complications, and the mechanisms of disease progression. Consideration of vascular and topographical relationships is of fundamental importance in assessing the risk of bleeding, perforation, and penetration. Anatomical variations can alter the clinical picture and influence the choice of diagnostic and treatment tactics.

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